

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Muon-Induced Events in Dynamic Operation (MIEDO)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA09-289
General application	<i>High-reliability ground level</i>
Type of test	<i>Single Event Effects</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Francisco J. Franco, Faculty of Physics, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Juan C. Fabero Hortensia Mecha Mohammadreza Rezaei Juan A. Clemente All the researchers above are with the Faculty of Computer Science, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>17-20 December 2025</i>
Facility	<i>ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, STFC Rutherford Appleton Laborator, Didcot (United Kingdom)</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	72

Objectives of the experiments

Muon-induced single event effects on SRAMs have been studied during the last fifteen years. Many issues have been solved, such as the dependence on the bias voltage, angle of incidence, energy/momentum, pattern, technology length, etc. Also, the different behaviour under positive and negative muons has drawn a lot of attention.

However, a review of the literature also shows that there are still many questions to be addressed. In fact, research have only dealt with static random access memories (SRAM) and anecdotally with Flash memories. Nothing about other devices such as DRAMs or FPGAs has been reported in the literature to our knowledge.

Another striking fact is that tests on SRAMs have only been done in static mode. This means that the memory is written with a predefined pattern, its bias voltage lowered, irradiated in sleep mode, and read back after raising the bias voltage to nominal values. This is interesting from a scientific point of view but it does not resembles the way these devices are supposed to work. Some works in the literature have shown that, under neutrons, the number of errors is higher if the memory is tested while performing dynamic tests such as March-C or D, and other single event different from SEUs can occur. Therefore, we consider that it is interesting to verify if the kind of operation is a key factor in irradiated SRAMs.

Initially, we proposed to test a 65-nm bulk CMOS 16-Mbit SRAM by Infineon. However, due to the

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release of more advanced models, we chose the 40-nm device instead.

Experiment test report

The first part of the experiment was satisfactorily performed. We started using positive muons and found that, according to simulations performed by the ISIS staff, the peak was to be found around 40 MeV/c. This value was just a first-order prediction since the structure and composition of materials was not fully understood. Finally, the peak was found at 42 MeV/c.

Next, we characterized the cross section for 42-MeV/c positive muons in proportion to the bias voltage and observed a decrease, but not as dramatical as expected. In other works, the cross section fell one order of magnitude every 400-500 mV but, in our experiments, the cross section for 2.6 V is hardly 1/20 that at 710 mV. This brings quite interesting consequences since positive muons could be a serious concern in commercial CMOS devices below this technology node (e.g., FPGA and microprocessors above 20 nm are built in this technology. Below, bulk CMOS is abandoned and FinFET used instead). It's worth indicating that the statistical properties of the set of logical addresses where flipped bits were observed is in fully agreement with an experiment where only single bit upsets occurred. Hence, despite multiple cell upsets are not ruled out, its importance is much lower than that of single bit upsets.

Cross section at 710 mV as a function of momentum

Cross section at 42 MeV/c in proportion to bias voltage.

Finally, several dynamic tests were performed at full speed by the microcontroller. These tests were March-C, Dynamic Classic, Dynamic Stress, MATS+, and mMATS+. Due to time constraints, only meaningful results were got for D.S., March-C and D.C. These results show that the regime of work is not a key issue to determine the cross section, and that all the events can be explained as direct interactions of muons with the individual memory cells. At any rate, let us keep in mind that the static cross section is unusually high. As in the case of static mode, only single bit upsets were registered.

Cross Sections for several Dynamic tests vs. static test.

Unfortunately, due to some issues in the proton beam, only about 1/3 of the devoted time was useful to gather experimental data. It would be useful to refine the value of the cross section in static mode at nominal bias voltage and, specially, to repeat the tests using negative muons. These particles are known to be much more dangerous than positive muons due to the occurrence of muon capture processes, leading to a higher cross section value that balance the lower flux. Also, the literature predicts the occurrence of multiple events with negative muons, and accurately predicted their absence with positive ones, as we have observed in our experiments.

NOTE: A good depiction of dynamic tests in SRAM can be found in:

L. Dilillo et al., "Soft errors in commercial off-the-shelf static random access memories" *Semiconductor Science and Technology*, IOP Publishing, 2016, 32, 013006, doi:10.1088/1361-6641/32/1/013006.

Besides, error bars were estimated using:

"Single Event Effects Test Method and Guidelines", *ESCC Basic Specification No. 25100*, by the European Space Agency and available on <https://escies.org/download/webDocumentFile?id=62690> for free download.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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